

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF A STRATEGIC PLAN FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGROTOURISM IN RURAL SETTLEMENTS OF OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation. This article deals with issues such as the need for the development of agrotourism in the regions, the need for rural tourism planning to lead agrotourism organizations, and ensuring effective competitiveness and economic well-being of agrotourism organizations, institutions, and clearly defining and clearly regulating strategies, tactics and mechanisms for working in market conditions.

Keywords. Tourism, agrotourism, Strategy, Strategic Plan, Network competitiveness.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются такие вопросы, как необходимость развития агротуризма в регионах, необходимость планирования сельского туризма для руководства организациями агротуризма, а также обеспечение эффективной конкурентоспособности и экономического благополучия организаций, учреждений агротуризма, а также четкое определение и регламентация стратегий, тактик и механизмов работы в рыночных условиях.

Ключевые слова. Туризм, агротуризм, Стратегия, стратегический план, конкурентоспособность сети.

The development of rural tourism requires specific planning. Planning is developed taking into account a clearly defined time frame using flexible modern integrated, environmentally friendly and sustainable methods. The biggest problem of planning at the level of private owners of agricultural properties is that they do not have special economic knowledge and appropriate skills in managing rural tourism. Tourism in rural areas is a private initiative sector, so the level of its planning should correspond to the general local and regional planning of the socio-economic and cultural development of rural communities.

The essence of the strategic planning of rural tourism is that it is the owner of an agricultural property, which must determine how its offer differs from the offer of potential competitors, potential opportunities, technologies and resources, branded services, corporate identity, etc.

Strategic planning should be considered as a dynamic set of interconnected management processes arising from each other.

This planning provides:

1. Rural agrotourism activity determination of the purpose of property - this process consists in determining the content of the activities of the farm, its purpose, characterizing the direction of activity based on market needs, Product Characteristics, the nature of its consumption, competitive conditions.

2. Assessment of the state of the environment involves the study of the influence of the following elements on agrofarmer farms: the state of the economy, the specifics of the legal

regulation of production, the characteristics of the environment and the availability of resources, the scientific and technical level, etc.

Market analysis involves identifying buyers, competitors and the labor market.

3. Assessment of the state of the internal structure makes it possible to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the farm, the internal capabilities that can be taken into account in the struggle for competition in the process of achieving their goals. The internal environment is studied in the following areas: Human Resources, Management Organization, marketing, finance.

4. Development of alternative solutions. They demonstrate a full spectrum of solutions, set the maximum possible set of options. Each option is associated with terms and resources, taking into account the limitations that may affect the decision. Factors that affect the following are considered important: obligations, the availability of financial resources and the provision of qualified personnel.

5. Justification and selection of the Optimal solution. This process is fundamental in strategic planning, as it decides how the company will achieve its goals and complete its tasks. The chosen strategy allows you to take into account all the factors that can affect its functioning.

6. Implementation of the Optimal solution and evaluation of the results. Assessing the implementation of an Optimal strategic decision is the final stage of strategic planning. The tool for ensuring objective assessment is control, which determines the system of control measures, determines the reasons for deviating the results of farm activities from a rational development strategy, allows you to make adjustments to the plan indicators and in the process of implementing the strategy.

Tourism planning is not a one-time action, but a continuous process in which planning is carried out sequentially and linearly, but dynamically. It corresponds to the characteristics of rural tourism as a large dynamic system with interconnected parts. A change in one factor, such as a tourist attraction, can affect all elements of tourism in the settlement: from services to advertising and transport. Similarly, changes in the leadership of local administration, business and non-profit organizations lead to new ideas, attract other assets, and tourists change with the development of tourist facilities.

Methodological recommendations for strategic planning of the development of rural tourism in the municipalities of our country have been developed to solve the established tasks.

In particular, after analyzing the main stages of the strategic plan, it was determined that the following stages can be included.

1. Analysis of the potential of the rural settlement.
2. Market analysis.
3. Formation of the touristic image of the rural settlement.
4. Defining specific goals and action plans.
5. Monitoring and evaluation of results (correction of plans if necessary).

Step 1. Analysis of tourism potential should provide the following information:

- whether the local population and management are ready to accept rural tourism as an opportunity to develop the economy of the settlement;
- to what extent the existing potential is being used;

- what opportunities are used in the organization of rural tourism and what problems may arise.

The purpose of the analysis is to identify the strengths and challenges of each element of the tourism system, including:

- attitudes and values of the local community;
- attractions and activities;
- commercial services;
- state institutions and services (infrastructure); transportation;
- communication;
- regulation and policy;
- local business climate and demographics;
- availability of buildings for public events.

In a rural settlement, tourism strengths are any tourism elements that attract, serve, assist or satisfy tourists. Each rural settlement has its own strong elements, such as a beautiful landscape, a cultural or historical attraction, the production of folk crafts or a recently expanded library. However, no element can be considered strong if it does not support tourism in some way.

It is not difficult to identify the general problems of tourism development. For example, if tourists do not stay long in the settlement, then it is necessary to understand why this happens (poor quality of guest houses, lack of free time, etc.). The more clearly the problems are identified, the easier it is to find ways to solve them. The same applies to strengths, the more clearly they are identified, the easier it is to develop them. The objectivity of community leaders is a prerequisite for assessing strengths and addressing challenges.

The key to understanding what a rural settlement can offer tourists is to look at the settlement from the perspective of potential visitors. What the villagers find attractive may be unattractive to the tourist. Conversely, what the villagers take for granted may be of great value to the tourist.

Commercial and municipal services, analysis of the infrastructure of settlements-this is an assessment of local enterprises and structures that serve tourists and achieve serious economic results. Therefore, it is necessary to make a detailed inventory of all guest houses, hotels, cafes, shops, pharmacies, car services, etc. During the inventory, it is necessary to pay attention to the convenient location of tourists; working hours and season; opportunities (cafes, attractions); the number of rooms available for living; proper training of employees, speed of Service and other features of the accounting services fund. If some services are not provided in the settlement, but there is a demand from tourists for them, it is worth thinking about how the problem will be solved. This can be the organization of cellular services or comprehensive services.

It is not enough to use a method that assumes that all tourists need the same information about attractions and services. They have become more selective in deciding where to travel.

Tourists need information in two cases:

- about the services offered before coming to the rural settlement;
- when you are in the settlement - information, signs, tours, interpretation of settlement maps.

Local people need knowledge about their communities and surroundings to be effective hosts. They can use it to make decisions about participation in entertainment events.

Local business representatives (tour operators of bus fleets, hotel managers) should be informed about travel, recreation and leisure in the rural settlement. It is important to consider the availability and accuracy of the following information:

- written information about the settlement;
- about the location of tourist places, prices and working hours of services and attractions;
- table of information centers;
- about trips to special places of interest (historical places, farms and hunting farms);
- what percentage of the tourism development budget is currently spent on advertising?

What market are they targeting? Are these actions effective?

- How familiar is the local population with the advertising materials of the settlement?

It should be remembered that communication in tourism is a two-way process. Promotion is carried from the rural settlements to the markets, and the marketing research of tourism companies ensures the flow of information from the markets to the return destinations.

All rural communities have norms or regulations that have a positive or negative impact on tourism development. State and federal regulations can play an important role in the development of tourism for both the public and private sectors.

Step 2. Market analysis.

In the second stage, two markets should be taken into account when planning tourism: tourist and local. When planning the development of rural tourism in a settlement, it is important to develop a local market for the local community. In addition to creating demand for companies and organizations that serve tourists, tourism markets are also important for those traveling to visit family and friends.

The general purpose of market research is to determine the necessary conditions for the full satisfaction of the population's demand for tourist services and their effective sale. Accordingly, the main task of market research is to assess the current ratio of supply and demand for tourist services, that is, market conditions.

The problem of formation of stable internal and external demand for rural tourism products is one of the main tasks of tourism development in Belgorod region. At the moment, infrastructure is being formed in the region with the efforts of state structures and rural entrepreneurs, and interesting proposals are emerging. However, the demand is still not regular.

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